

Comparative Analysis of Various Antibiotics in Surgical Site Infections Caused by Various Causative Microorganisms

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Abstract

Introduction: Surgical Site Infections could involve an organ or bodily space, a shallow or deep incisional infection, or both. The third most frequently reported nosocomial infection in the hospital population, postoperative SSI is one of the most frequent issues for patients, who receive cesarean sections. The prevalence of postoperative SSI varies significantly across procedures, hospitals, doctors, patients, and geographical locales. It makes things more difficult worldwide including Ethiopia (21%), India (2.85%), and Nigeria (7-9.6%).

Aims and Objectives: To analyze the efficacy in terms of sensitivity and resistance of various antibiotics in the management of surgical site infection with respect to the causal organisms.

Methods: This is a prospective study conducted on 430 patients. In addition, out of 430 patients were operated on for clean surgeries, clean-contaminated surgeries, contaminated surgeries. The postoperative wound discharge was collected and bacterial pathogens were isolated. The plates were incubated at 37°C overnight for 24-48 hours. A hand lens was used whenever necessary to inspect all plate cultures.

Results: The study found that a total of 430 patients were studied for the development of Post-Operative Surgical Site Infection. It has been found that 32 out of 430 cases showed growth of 36 isolates, with overall post-operative surgical site infection rate of 7.47%. The study found 100% resistance is present in *Klebsiella*, *E. coli* with ampicillin while amikacin and gentamicin have 100% resistance with Acinetobacter.

Conclusion: The study has shown sensitivity and resistance of different antibiotics with different micro-organisms and have brought forward an image of epidemiological view of surgical site infection, all of which, would contribute in the postoperative management efficiently.

Keywords: Surgical Site Infection, *Klebsiella*, Nosocomial Infection

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Introduction

An infection at the surgical site that affects the incision or deeper tissues within 30 days of the procedure (or within a year if

the implantation is left in place just after the procedure) is referred to as a surgical site infection (SSI) [1]. These infections

could involve an organ or bodily space, a shallow or deep incisional infection, or both. The third most frequently reported nosocomial infection in the hospital population, postoperative SSI is one of the most frequent issues for patients who receive cesarean sections. Following a cesarean section, postoperative SSI is linked to higher rates of morbidity and death, extended hospital stays, secondary infertility, and higher patient care costs [2]. The prevalence of postoperative SSI varies significantly across procedures, hospitals, doctors, patients, and geographical locales. It makes things more difficult in Ethiopia (21%), India (2.85%), and Nigeria (7-9.6%) [3,4]. *Staphylococcus aureus*, which accounts for 20–30% of SSIs that occur in hospitals, is a frequently isolated bacteria in SSIs. Additionally, gram-negative *Bacilli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Klebsiella*, as well as *E. coli* are frequently isolated from SSIs [5].

Improved operating room airflow, sterilization techniques, the utilization of barriers, surgical techniques, and the provision of antimicrobial prophylaxis are some of the SSI control strategies that have advanced. Despite this, SSIs continue to happen and are frequently the cause of mortality and morbidity in hospitals, primarily in developing nations [6]. The rise of pathogenic microorganisms that are resistant to antibiotics is one factor in this. According to reports, protracted labor prior to a cesarean section, prolonged membrane rupture, frequent vaginal examinations, being un-booked, and protracted obstructed labor are major risk factors for cesarean wound infection [7,8] Other factors include the surgeon's lack of experience or poor technique, the length of the operation, the length of the labor's obstruction, the postoperative anemia, the patient's high BMI, the presence of diabetes mellitus, the presence of immunosuppressive disorders, and some medications, such as steroid [9].

Additionally, our environment has a greater prevalence of surgical infections due to lax infection control and prevention procedures in the operating room. The following have been highlighted as potential sources of infection: polluted air, antiseptic solutions, patient transportation, the surgical team, crowded operating rooms, theater gowns, poorly sterilized equipment, polluted environment, and severely contaminated surfaces [10]. SSI complications include pelvic abscess, necrotizing fasciitis, ruptured abdomen, wound dehiscence, and protracted wound healing. Among the others include protracted admission, a protracted duration of antibiotics, the potential for re-admission, second repair surgery, post-operative hernia, permanently damaging scar, and in rare circumstances, can result in severe sepsis and death. The physical, emotional, social, and financial facets of life are all negatively impacted by surgical site infections [11].

Bacteriological research has demonstrated the universality of SSIs and the possibility of diverse etiological agents depending on the geographical area, the surgery, the surgeon, the hospital, or even the ward [12]. Gram-negative organisms have become more common in recent years as a major source of dangerous infections in many hospitals. AMR, which results from the inappropriate use of broad-spectrum antibiotics, has further aggravated the situation in this regard. In impoverished nations, the issue is made more challenging by subpar infection control procedures, congested hospitals, and inappropriate antimicrobial use [13,14].

Materials and Methods

Research design

This is a prospective study conducted in the Department of Microbiology and Dr DY Patil Hospital Nerul, Navi Mumbai from July, 2021 to June, 2022 the study was conducted on 430 patients. In addition, out of 430 patients were operated

on for clean surgeries, clean-contaminated surgeries, contaminated surgeries, and unclean surgeries. The post-operative wound discharge was collected by using sterile swab. All the swabs were immediately transported to the laboratory for further processing. A smear was prepared from post-operative wound swab. That smear was stained by Gram staining method for preliminary identification of the bacteria. For isolation of bacterial pathogens, the swabs from postoperative wounds were inoculated on 5% Sheep Blood agar, MacConkey's agar, and Chocolate agar. The plates were incubated at 37°C overnight for 24-48 hours. A hand lens was used, whenever necessary to inspect all plate cultures.

Inclusion and Exclusion criteria

Among 430 patients, who had clean surgeries, clean-contaminated surgeries, contaminated surgeries, and dirty surgeries. For elective surgeries, patients signed the consent and followed up after surgeries. In addition, out of 430 patients were operated on for clean surgeries, clean-contaminated surgeries, contaminated surgeries, and dirty

surgeries. In addition, Emergency surgeries, Stitch abscesses, and patients that did not follow up post-surgeries.

Statistical analysis

The study has used MS Excel for effective analysis. The continuous variables were expressed as mean±standard deviation. The discrete variables were expressed as counts and its respective percentage.

Ethical Approval

The study was explained to each of the patient before collection of data and blood. The Ethical Committee of the hospital approved the study process. The researchers obtained and stored written consent from each patient.

Results

A total of 36 organisms are isolated from post-operative Infections, Single organisms are isolated from multiple cases. Out of these 430 cases were classified as general surgery, orthopedics, OBGY, CVTs and Pediatric surgery. The subsequent analysis has been classified it different categories in Table 1.

Table 1: Ward-wise/department-wise distribution of organisms and number of patients infected with each micro-organism

Organisms	General surgery	Orthopedics	OBGY	CVTs	Pediatric Surgery
<i>Kleb. Spp.</i>	8	2	2	0	0
<i>E. coli</i>	3	2	2	1	0
<i>S. aureus</i>	3	0	1	1	1
<i>Enterococcus</i>	2	1	0	0	0
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	3	0	0	0	0
<i>Acinetobacter</i>	1	1	1	0	0
Cons	1	0	0	0	0
Total	21	6	6	2	1

Throughout this analysis, a total of 430 patients were studied for the development of Post-Operative Surgical Site Infection. 32 out of 430 cases showed growth of 36 isolates, with overall post-operative surgical site infection rate of 7.47%. The following analysis has presented Sensitivity % among isolates no in Table

2. From above Table 2 amongst the *Klebsiella* spp. isolates of *K. pneumoniae* were obtained and 1 isolate of *K. oxytoca* was obtained. *K. oxytoca* showed resistance to only Ampicillin. Table 2 shows the detailed findings of each antibiotic with each micro-organism.

Table 2: Antibiotic Sensitivity of each micro-organism with respective antibiotics

Anti-biotics	<i>Klebsiella</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>Enterococcus</i>	<i>P. aerugin</i>	<i>Acinetobacter</i>
Ampicillin	0	0	100%			
Amikacin	6(54%)	100%	2(33.4%)		100%	0
Gentamicin	6(54%)	100%	1(16.6%)			0
Imipenem	6(54%)	7(87.5%)	1(16.6%)			
Meropenem	6(54%)	7(87.5%)				
Piperacillin	3(27%)	5(62.5%)	0		100%	0
Tazobactam		5(62.5%)			100%	0
Cefotaxime	0	0	2(33.4%)			0
Ceftriaxone	0	0		1(33.4%)		0
Cefepime	3(23%)	2(25%)	1(16.6%)		1(33%)	0
Ciprofloxacin	4(36%)	6(75%)	1(16.6%)		100%	1(33%)
Ceftazidime/Clavulanic acid	0	0			1(33%)	0

430 patients were studied for the development of Post-Operative Surgical Site Infection. The study found 100% resistance is present in *Klebsiella*, *E. coli* with ampicillin while amikacin and gentamicin have 100% resistance with *Acinetobacter*. Through the Table 3 discussion, this study has presented Resistance % among isolates

Table 3: Antibiotic Resistance of each micro-organism with respective antibiotics

Anti-biotics	<i>Klebsiella</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>Enterococcus</i>	<i>P. aeruginos</i>	<i>Acinetobacter</i>
Ampicillin	100%	100%				
Amikacin	5(46%)	0			0	100%
Gentamicin	5(46%)	0				100%
Imipenem	5(46%)	1(12.5%)				
Meropenem	5(46%)	1(12.5%)				
Piperacillin	8(73%)	3(37.5%)			0	
Tazobactam		3(37.5%)			0	
Cefotaxime	100%	100%	4(66.6%)			100%
Ceftriaxone	100%	100%		2(66.6%)		100%
Cefepime	8(73%)	6(75%)	5(83.3%)		2(67%)	100%
Ciprofloxacin	7(64%)	2(25%)	5(83.3%)		0	2(67%)
Ceftazidime/Clavulanic acid	100%	100%			2(67%)	100%

Discussion

The major reason for surgical site infections (SSI) in the U. S. is *S. aureus*. Particularly, SSI brought about by methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) has evolved into a severe complication, increasing fatality rates, length of hospital stays, and expenses. Addressing modifiable factors and

choosing and administering antibiotic prophylaxis at the proper time are effective strategies for preventing SSI caused by *S. aureus*. Vancomycin usage and other methods like decolonization are still debatable [15-17].

In a medical center in Gondar, northwestern Ethiopia, surgical wound infections were observed over the course

of a year to determine their frequency and pattern. In fifty (38.9%) of the 129 abdominal surgery incisions from 130 patients, harmful organisms were found. On purely clinical criteria, the wound rate of infection was 22.7%. With the highest prevalence of infection being 61.7% for polluted or filthy wounds, wound class was substantially linked with infection rates. Both emergency or elective operations had the same infection rate. The majority of pathogenic isolates were caused by *S. aureus* and *Escherichia* 13.9% of patients' delays in being discharged were due to surgical wound infection [18]

The most common orthopedic emergency among elderly people is a femoral neck fracture. No multicenter investigation comparing antibiotic prophylaxis techniques and the frequency and microbiological features of surgical site infection (SSI) has been carried out in France, despite the high incidence of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) transmission in this group. This concludes MRSA is the most commonly detected causative infection and causes severe SSI following surgery for a femoral neck fracture. To ascertain if the use of MRSA-effective antibiotic prophylaxis will lower the SSI rate in this cohort, a sizable, major alternative trial is required [19].

Surgical site infection (SSI) is still a major issue that can have a severe impact on clinical outcomes after surgery. Most of the time, microbiology results are comparable to those of other nosocomial diseases; nevertheless, there may be variances depending on the microbiology selected owing to drug pressure or resident flora. However, in the context of critical care, this is not well understood. Consequently, our goal was to evaluate the prevalence, epidemiology, or microbiology of SSI and its relationship to mortality in patients suffering from severe pancreatitis in the critical care unit (ICU) [20,21].

Results of antibiotic susceptibility tests revealed that the vast majority of the isolated bacteria had high levels of resistance²³. The most efficient antibiotics against gram-positive bacteria were determined to be vancomycin, teicoplanin, linezolid, and amikacin. The gram-negative bacteria showed even higher levels of resistance, and it was shown that the regularly used medications had higher levels of resistance, with an average resistance range of 50% to 100%. Ampicillin, amoxicillin-clavulanate, and cefotaxime were among the most resistant medications, whereas meropenem, piperacillin-tazobactam, and amikacin were determined to be the most effective antimicrobial agents [22,23].

Current guidelines for antibiotic therapy to prevent SSI propose starting an antibiotic treatment 60 minutes before surgery and stopping it immediately after. But more than half of our people received preoperative antibiotics more than 6 hours prior to surgery, and nearly all of them received antibiotic treatment afterward [24]. In an effort to stop infection while they were in the hospital, many of them had been even treated up to the day of release. The most popular combination was an aminoglycoside and a third-generation cephalosporin. The bacterial isolates strains were mainly resistant to these drugs, however, according to the findings of the antimicrobial susceptibility tests. Nearly all isolates consistently showed the highest level of ampicillin resistance, and this was determined to be statistical significance for all but one *Proteus* species [25,26].

Conclusion

The study has concluded that *K. pneumonia* were 56% Susceptible to Amikacin, Gentamicin, Meropenem and Imipenem, *E. coli* showed 100% susceptibility to Amikacin and Gentamicin, followed-by 87.5% susceptibility to Meropenem and

Imipenem. The Enterobacteriaceae were 100% ESBL producers. *P. aeruginosa* were 100% susceptible to Amikacin, Tobramycin and Ciprofloxacin followed by 67% sensitivity to Imipenem. The Gram-positive bacteria were 100% susceptible to Linezolid. A plethora of risk factors contributed to post-operative surgical wound infections. Marked resistance of isolates to commonly used antibiotics made the need for judicious and rational use of these drugs to prevent emergence of antibiotic resistant strains.

Hence, this study has brought forward significant findings, which would contribute to post-operative management and prevent surgical site infection.

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